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Pride and Perseverance: A Historical Overview of Lesbian Resistance in Kerala

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Abstract:

Kerala is a state in India recognized for its liberal social policies; despite the progressive outlooks, the queer community continues to face discrimination and marginalization. Individuals belonging to diverse gender identities and sexual orientations still encounter social inequalities which undermine their mental health and physical well-being. This paper examines the resistance and activism employed by lesbian individuals and organizations in their efforts as a collective to promote their rights and to challenge heteronormativity. It also examines how collective identity shapes the resistive movements of queer people and how it challenges the existing dominant power structures. Analyzing lesbian resistance as a collective resistance will uncover how minorities of shared identity shape their strategies for equality and empowerment. Lesbians working collectively facilitate positive social change by resisting the systemic oppression faced by sexual minorities. A

detailed examination of strategies employed in lesbian activism to advocate for equal rights offers critical insights into the diverse obstacles encountered by the lesbian community in Kerala.

Keywords: Queer activism, Gender, Sexuality, Lesbian resistance, Heteronormativity.

Queer resistance in India has been marked by struggle and resilience. Queer communities in India have constantly challenged the discriminatory laws and societal taboos against queer people. The struggle of the queer community has been shaped through ongoing resistance against patriarchal structures and cultural conservatism. Heteronormative power structures have historically marginalized the queer community. Historically, the community has faced discrimination and is vulnerable to violence and bullying. They often live in fear of being rejected by their own family and society, yet they have fought against these systems of oppression through activism and resistance.

Over the past few years, Kerala has witnessed a notable surge in lesbian activism, making it an essential region for studying the challenges, struggles and achievements of lesbian communities. Understanding lesbian resistance will undoubtedly help in uncovering how they challenge patriarchal norms and fight for their rights. Kerala is known for its progressive mindset, but even then, lesbian women and queer people in general continue to face discrimination. Studying lesbian resistance in Kerala will offer insights into the working of gender and sexuality, particularly within the context of a highly patriarchal and heteronormative society.

Lesbians have been historically marginalized and restricted in India as it is a predominantly patriarchal society. The power dynamics are centred on male dominance in a patriarchal society, and it demands conformity to traditional sexual and gender roles, especially from women. The heteronormative notion of sexuality works to uphold patriarchy in a society like that of India, and

any non-normative sexuality is seen as a threat. Lesbian and queer organizations play a crucial role in empowering queer resistance as it provides for community building and activism. These organizations act as a space for lesbians to meet, share their experiences and work for common goals and issues. These networks of support highlight the collective identity among sexually marginalized people. The idea of collective identity was developed by the Italian historian Alberto Melucci. Through collective identity theory, he explains how marginalized groups with similar goals can actually bring about social change. Individuals working collectively construct action by “means of ‘organized’ investments: they define in cognitive terms the field of possibilities and limits they perceive while at the same time activating their relationships so as to give sense to their ‘being together’ and to the goals they pursue” (Melucci 43). In the case of lesbian and queer organizations, they play an important role in challenging heteronormative power structures by actively working against the conforming norms of gender and sexuality. They also organize protests and advocate for equal rights to bring about change in society.

Lesbians are often marginalized to maintain the traditional gender roles and power dynamics in society, as pointed out by Adrienne Rich in her essay “Compulsory Heterosexuality and Lesbian Existence”. Heteronormativity oppresses women and restricts the agency of women by forcefully enforcing compulsory heterosexuality on them. It normalizes heterosexuality, and non-normative sexualities are seen as unnatural. Rich emphasizes the importance of acknowledging lesbian existence and argues that it “comprises both the breaking of a taboo and the rejection of a compulsory way of life” (27). Monique Wittig argues that the social system of heteronormativity is oppressive to women by its very nature. It uses the notion of difference between sexes to justify the oppression towards women. She advocates challenging heteronormative ideologies so as to create inclusive space for free gender and sexual expression.

Wittig, in her essay “The Straight Mind” famously stated that “Lesbians are not Women” (32). Through this statement, she critiques the existing heteronormative system which conforms individuals to traditional gender and sexual norms. Lesbian exists outside this system as they reject to conform to the heteronormative standards. Wittig argues that lesbians are located beyond the ‘categories of sex’ and are “able to run away from their class (the class of women), even if only partially and precariously” (47). For her, being a lesbian is inherently a form of resistance.

The lesbian resistance for equal rights in India remains an ongoing process. The decriminalization of section 377 of the Indian Penal Code in September 2018 has been a significant milestone in the struggle for queer rights in India. Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code was introduced during the colonial period of India when the Indian Law Commission was presided over by Lord Macaulay. The section reads, “Whoever voluntarily has carnal intercourse against the order of nature with any man, woman, or animal shall be punished with imprisonment for life or with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to ten years, and shall be liable to fine” (“Section 377 Unnatural offences”). This law not only restricted the personal freedom of queer individuals but also reinforced the existing stigma and taboo against non-heterosexual identities, making it difficult for them to gain visibility and acceptance. The legal barrier that was caused by this section has adversely affected the queer community as they were not able to freely advocate for their rights.

Decriminalization of Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code has been a long struggle for the LGBTQIA+ community. Over the years, many legal battles have been fought against this in the court. One of the major battles was the Naz Foundation case. The Naz Foundation is a non-governmental organization for LGBTQIA+ in India that works on AIDS and other sexual issues (Shalini). They petitioned against the unconstitutional nature of section 377 in the Delhi High

Court in 2001. The Naz Foundation argued that Section 377 “is in violation of the fundamental rights to equal protection under the law as well as to life and liberty, which the group claimed includes a right to privacy” (Dave 179). In 2009, the Delhi High Court declared that Section 377 was unconstitutional to the extent that it violated Article 14, Article 15, and Article 21 of the Indian Constitution (Shahani). This case was a significant step towards the decriminalization of homosexual acts and was appealed to the Supreme Court.

It was the Navtej Singh Johar v. Union of India case that became crucial in decriminalizing homosexual sex. In 2016, Navtej Singh filed a case for the decriminalization of homosexual relations, stating that it violated the fundamental rights of citizens of India. In the Navtej case, “the court realized that interfering with an individual’s private affairs would violate the right to privacy. Based on the realization, the Navtej Judgement recognized that the right to union is intrinsic to Article 21 of the constitution, and union does not merely refer to marriage but also companionship, which is physical, mental, sexual, and emotional” (Mehrotra). In a historic judgement of this case, the Supreme Court of India read down the parts of Section 377 that decriminalized homosexual acts between consenting adults. The recognition of the fundamental rights of the queer community to express themselves and live freely without fear of persecution was brought about by this historic ruling. The legalizing of consensual homosexual acts represented a significant advancement in the struggle of the queer people in India. Though discrimination against homosexuals still exists in India, this has been a major step towards equality for queer people. Discrimination and prejudice against the queer community still exist in the areas of marriage, work and healthcare. Same-sex marriage and civil union of homosexuals are still not legal in India. As same-sex marriage cannot be legally registered, homosexual partners are denied the benefits and rights enjoyed by heterosexual couples.

Lesbian identities and relationships have existed since ancient times, though they may have been expressed and understood differently than they are today. In pre-colonial India, there was a greater degree of openness and acceptance of diverse sexualities and gender identities. Rohit R Dasgupta points out that many instances of lesbian relationships can be seen in Indian literature, including in the Bengali text *Kritivasa Ramayana* (653). Things changed with the coming of the British. The colonial period of India underwent a major shift from minor intolerance of homosexuality to a widespread condemnation of homosexuality. This evident shift was seen in the British interpretation of the traditional indigenous texts and in the formal prohibition of sodomy in India. Lauren Ruhnke writes,

The language of Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code, which prohibits all “carnal intercourse against the order of nature,” leaves ample room for liberal interpretation of what constitutes an act of sodomy. The phrase “against the law of nature” came to mean against the British moral standards that inspired the laws of the Indian Penal Code and thus enabled British courts to prosecute natives on the basis of their Inherent unnaturalness. (89-90).

In the wake of the decriminalization of same-sex relationships between consenting adults in India, numerous lesbian women have voiced their protest against the restrictive societal norms. The decriminalization of same-sex relationships has made a huge difference in the lives of lesbian women in India, including the women of Kerala. It has empowered lesbian women to live the life they want and gave them the freedom to challenge the existing heteronormative assumptions that constrain their lives.

In her work, *Queer Activism in India: A Story in the Anthropology of Ethics*, anthropologist Naisargi N. Dave argues that “lesbian activism in India is much more of an activism of invention than resistance” (12). She suggests that lesbian activism is not just radical opposition to the existing power structures but mainly aims at the imaginative creation of possibilities within the existing structure, where they can forge their own space. Along with fighting against the injustices, lesbian activism also engages in making their own spaces in relation to society to create a more inclusive and safe space for the lesbian and queer community. Lesbian activists mainly do this by forming organizations and communities, as they are fundamental to the lesbian resistance. In the face of societal discrimination and taboos, these communities provide a vital space for support and shared advocacy.

Sahayatrika is one of the most prominent organizations advocating for queer women’s rights in Kerala. Founded by Deepa Vasudevan, a Malayali immigrant to Canada, this organization strives to help transgender, lesbian, and bisexual women from Kerala. Sahayatrika was initially established in response to the alarming increase in lesbian suicide rates in Kerala. More than thirty lesbian suicide cases were reported in the period of ten years (Mohan). There were no organizations dedicated to advocating for the rights of women with non-heterosexual desires. Driven by this realization, she founded an organization specifically for addressing the needs of lesbian and bisexual women in Kerala. Sahayatrika provided support and resources to lesbians in need and worked to create a more inclusive and accepting society for sexual and gender minorities. P Agaja says,

The formation of the organization was an important landmark in the history of the queer movement in Kerala because, prior to this, there was no formal and public platform for sexual minorities in Kerala to express their non-normative gender and sexual identities.

The developmental discourses in Kerala have largely ignored the concerns of sexual minorities (88).

Queerythm is an organization for queer community from the Thiruvananthapuram district of Kerala. Queerythm regularly hosts monthly meetings and provides a safe space for dialogue, shared experiences, and mutual understanding for queer people. Over time, this movement evolved into a registered community-based organization, becoming a champion for queer rights (Harikumar). In 2021, Queerythm, along with Dhisha, another queer organization, jointly filed a case against the National Medical Commission (NMC) and the Undergraduate Medical Education Board (UMEB) in the Kerala High Court (Joseph). The petitioners challenged the discriminatory and derogatory content in the textbooks prescribed for medical courses in Kerala, arguing that it promoted unscientific views about queer community. It was argued that “the curriculums prepared by National Medical Commission and Under Graduate Medical Education Board, have labelled ‘homosexuality and lesbianism’ under ‘unnatural sexual offence, sexual perversion and paraphilia’. The curriculum also teaches ‘homosexuality’ as a sexual disorder, and ‘transgenderism’ is taught under ‘gender identity disorder’” (Joseph). They further stated that they had already raised concerns about this content with the NMC and UMEB, but no action had been taken. The Kerala High Court addressed this as a grave issue and directed the UMEB to consider removing the objectionable content from the textbooks immediately. This remains a landmark win for Queerythm, Dhisha, and the queer community in Kerala.

Queerala is an important organization for queer people in Kerala, established in 2013. They offer support to individuals belonging to sexual and gender minorities. They actively advocate for queer rights, promoting equality and inclusivity. They provide mental health support and counselling to queer people who requires assistance. Queerala’s online website offers blogs, news

and resources related to queer people. Their website provides details of Mental health practitioners who have completed Queer Affirmative Counselling Practice. It also provides details of peer supporters of the LGBTQI+ community and details of Queer-Trans collectives (“Queerala”).

Rainbow Club is a pioneering college queer club founded in 2023. It was established in Government College, Chittur, in Palakkad district of Kerala. Rainbow Club regularly organizes activities, campaigns, discussions, talks, and workshops to raise awareness among students about queer rights. The club also raises awareness about the issues and discrimination faced by queer people, and it promotes equality for all. One of the major events conducted by Rainbow Club was ‘Come Out Palakkad’, which was held at Fort Maidan in Palakkad. It was grand both in its scale and its impact, as many students of most colleges in the district came together to draw huge graffiti on the walls of Fort Maidan in support of queer rights. This event was supported by the Palakkad District Administration and the Zilla Panchayat. Another important initiative of Rainbow Club is the making of a handbook for queer affirmative and queer friendly campuses. The club collaborates with Kerala Youth Leadership Academy and Prism, an inclusivity project of the Government of Kerala, in the making of the handbook. (“Training Module”).

In addition to the efforts made by numerous organizations, individual acts of resistance have also benefited the queer community. In the case of Sreeja S v. Commissioner of Police in 2018, the Kerala High Court made a seminal judgement, stating that the separation of adults engaged in a consensual relationship, irrespective of their sexual orientation, violates constitutional rights. The petitioner, Sreeja was in a lesbian relationship with Aruna. Aruna’s parents refused to accept her sexuality, and she left to live with Sreeja. When Aruna was taken into custody by her parents and forcibly took her to a mental health facility, Sreeja filed a writ of Habeas Corpus seeking Aruna's release. During the proceedings, Aruna admitted to being in a relationship with

Sreeja and expressed her desire to live with her. The court upheld Aruna's choice and granted her freedom. The Supreme Court of India acknowledged this case in its publication titled 'Sensitisation Module for the Judiciary on LGBTIQ+ Community', citing this case as an effective response to the challenges faced by queer individuals within the justice system due to marginalization (Ameerudheen). Sensitization Module for the Judiciary on LGBTIQ+ Community is a handbook published by the Supreme Court of India to sensitize judges, judicial staff and citizens about the queer community in India.

A notable instance of lesbian resistance in Kerala, which gained popularity in social media and also among the general public, was initiated by the lesbian couple Adhila Nasarin and Fathima Noora. They faced disapproval from their parents as they were engaged in a romantic relationship. Adhila and Noora both faced physical and mental abuse from their parents. They sought refuge at a Safe Home in Kozhikode with support from the NGO Vanaja Collective, but later, Fathima Noora was unlawfully confined by her parents, which led Adhila to file a missing person's report. The Thamarassery Police refused to intervene in this case, citing it as a family matter. Adhila later filed a case in the Kerala High Court. In *Adhila Nasarin v. State Commissioner of Police*, the Kerala High Court allowed them to live together, as per their choice. The Vanaja Collective provided essential emotional and legal support to the couple (John).

A recent case of lesbian resistance is that of Sumayya Sherin and Afeefa C S. Sumayya and Afeefa belonged to a conservative Muslim family, and their parents were against their relationship. Sumayya and Afeefa sought help from the Vanaja Collective to live together in 2023. Following Malappuram magistrates' court's affirmation of their right to cohabit, they both settled in Ernakulam. However, Afeefa's family forcibly took her, leading Sumayya to file a missing person's complaint. Subsequently, the Kerala High Court ordered Afeefa's production, but in the

court, she chose to be with her parents. It was later exposed that Afeefa had to face mental and physical violence from her family. Afeefa revealed that she was forced to undergo conversion therapy and that her statement against Sumayya in court was not according to her will. Vanaja Collective intervened, leading to Afeefa's rescue ("Kerala HC"). The court intervened to safeguard the couple and granted them needed protection and permission to live according to their choice.

The lesbian activism in Kerala has come a long way. By analyzing the lesbian resistive movements, we can see that both collective activism and personal resistance have contributed to the progress of lesbian movements in Kerala. In light of Alberto Melucci's idea of collective identity, it becomes clear that for resistive movements to work, individual and collective efforts need to come together. This collective resistance has paved the way for advancement in queer rights. The overview of lesbian resistance in Kerala highlights that this interplay between individual and collective actions played a crucial role in the evolution of lesbian activism. By embracing shared experiences and goals, queer individuals have collaborated collectively towards their goal of sexual and gender equality. This study of lesbian activism reveals the mechanisms through which marginalized groups articulate their identity and advocate for their rights. It provides a practical framework for advancing queer rights, which will be helpful for future activism. By using different strategies, such as advocacy awareness programs, activists have questioned homophobic narratives and championed queer rights.

The lesbian resistive movements in Kerala have not just helped to create awareness of the complexities of sexuality but also have promoted inclusivity and representation. In Kerala, media outreach and storytelling have also significantly helped in increasing lesbian visibility. Lesbian activists and queer people have shared their experiences and communicated their stories through writings and interviews. This has effectively raised awareness and fostered a sense of empathy and

understanding among the general public. Queer people have resisted the existing power structures and continue to do so. Despite these resistances, Lesbian has still a long way to go. Same-sex marriage is still not legal in India, and discrimination against the lesbian community still persists. Even with these struggles, the lesbian community is slowly but surely moving towards its goal of achieving full acceptance in society.

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